

Automatic sugar beet thinner equipped with machine vision

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Abstract

Thinning is one of the most tedious and exhaustive operations in row-crop plant cultivation. It is mostly done manually by employing many labours during hot days in summer. In this study, a pneumatic mechanism was developed to automatically root up the redundant plants to provide enough space for the remaining sugar beet plants. The algorithm designed for thinning the sugar beet plants when there is significant overlapping between the adjacent plants. Retaining the single plants untouched was regarded in the algorithm not to diminish the overall yield of the field due to bare spaces. The performance of the machine was investigated at three different levels of forward speeds. Results showed that the best accuracy of the machine in providing the desired thinning distance between the remaining crops was gained at the speed of 2 and 3.5 km/hr. The machine also achieved well in leaving the single plants untouched with an accuracy of 99.1% while the speed did not have a significant influence on this achievement. Both laboratory and field experiments showed a reasonable performance which encourages the use of automatic thinning for sugar beet cultivation.

Background

Thinning is one of the most laborious and exhaustive operations in row-crop plant cultivation. It is mostly done manually by employing many labours during hot days in summer.

The first stage before the thinning is the plant detection which can be done both with machine visions in the visible spectrum or utilizing the differences between the reflected spectrums of the soil and plants as a tool for discrimination. At the early stages of growth when the sugar beet plants are small, no occlusion and overlapping between the adjacent plants exist. In this stage, it is possible to use the spot spectral sensor for plant detection (Palmer and Owen, 1971).

To avoid unplanted spaces in the field, it is preferred to sow the seeds with very close distances then it would be possible to singulate the plants by removing the surplus plants. However this method of cultivation assures the even coverage of the field, makes difficulty for using spectral methods.

The dramatic difference between the visual features of sugar beet and soil has provided the chance to use machine vision for thinning purposes.

Although thinning methods are similar in overall look, they may have differences due to management aspects and decision made by farmers. In consequence, the thinning algorithms also may have different designs. Ahmadi Moghaddam et al. (2016) designed two methods of using shape centroid and width of the crop in their algorithm while they find out the width of the crop method had better performance when the overlapping between plants is high.

To provide a suitable space between the sugar beet plants to let the beet to grow freely, several methods of cultivation are tried. While in good irrigation and soil conditions seeds are sown in the considered location at the beginning, in some cases, seeds are sown very close to each other to make it possible to choose the best distance between the grown plants. This method is suitable when there is a risk of unsown regions due to harsh soil condition or over irrigation. Therefore thinning the extra plants would be a requisite in this kind of cultivation.

The objectives of this study were to evaluate the performance of the thinning machine in terms of accuracy in providing the desired space between the crops and evaluate the effect of forward speed on the accuracy of thinning to determine the potential working capacity of the thinning machine.

Methods

In this study, a pneumatic mechanism was developed to automatically root up the redundant plants to provide enough space for the remaining sugar beet plants. Thinning machine (Figure 1) was designed so that two transecting blades to cut the weeds at about 10 cm below the soil surface where most of the weed root could be cut.

Figure 1. Thinning machine designed for this study

The machine consisted of three main parts including machine vision unit, electronic control unit, and thinning actuators. In the machine vision part, the main task was designing the algorithm so that to be able to provide a suitable space between the plants whereas considering unsown regions. The output of the vision system was a signal sent to the control unit. A rotary encoder mounted on a ground wheel was used to determine the accurate position of the plant respect to the camera. The signal received from the computer is kept in the electronic control unit until a specific number of signals - corresponding to the distance between the scene and actuators- was passed. Then the signal would be sent to the solenoid valve to open the pressurized air toward the pneumatic jacks. The pneumatic jack would get closed again after a specific number of signals- corresponding to the width of a sugar beet plant- was passed.

The two main tasks considered for the machine vision part were segmentation of the plants from the background soil and sending the actuation signal to the microcontroller based on the thinning algorithm. Machine vision codes were written in LabVIEW environment.

Plant detection was based on the excessive green algorithm which has shown reasonable performance in differentiating between the soil and green plants (Woebbecke et al., 1995; Jafari et al. 2006; Kiani & Jafari, 2008).

Surplus plants were removed through the algorithm designed for machine vision system to consider a desirable distance about 20 cm between the plants. Triggering the thinning signal relies on the distance between the two successive strips in the image. Image acquisition intervals were based on the signals received from the incremental encoder mounted on a ground wheel.

To evaluate the performance of the thinning machine, field experiments were conducted in three levels of forward speeds of 2, 3.5 and 5 km/h.

Results and discussion

Experiments were conducted in two phases in the laboratory and in the field. In the laboratory, the response time and delay of the system from seeing to execution was measured. The measurements were carried out on the green paper pieces lying on the ground with different designs and spaces between.

Response time

Measurements carried out on 100 images with resolutions of 640×480 pixel showed that the average processing time of an image was 51.32 milliseconds. These measurements were done through the time measurement routines in the program. It was also seen that the average time needed to capture an image was 14.45 millisecond. The response time of the electronic control unit was measured using 40 images.

The delay time of micro controller and mechanical actuators were 62.12 and 207.87 milliseconds which made a total delay of the thinning system to be 335.77 milliseconds. As it was expected the delay of the mechanical parts constituted the major part of the system delay. Therefore the attempt in reducing the delay time of the system showed be mainly focused in this part. These response times are important for on time action of the tines.

Measurement of the speed of the pneumatic jacks in opening and closing showed that the opening delay in the laboratory tests (out of the soil) was lower than that of closing while in the field experiments it was adverse. The reason was the difference between the forces needed to open and close the tine in the soil and out of the soil.

Normally, the delay time of these components are constant and irrelevant to the forward speed of the thinning machine but the temporal distance between the plant location and where the actuators act, depends on the forward speed. Therefore, in total, determining the exact time of the action will be dependent on the speed. The effect of different speeds on the accuracy of the tines in action is shown in table 1.

Table 1. Comparing the effect of different forward speeds on the delay of the tine action

Forward speed (km/hr)	Mean lead (mm)	Mean lag (mm)
2	13.37 ^a	10.0* ^C
3.5	12.83 ^a	24.42 ^B
5	0 ^b	63.41 ^A

Similar letters in each column indicate that there is no significant difference between the groups (at 5% significance)

In addition to the aforementioned reasons, slippage of the ground wheel, the rugged ground of the field, and vibrations can produce lag and lead in the action time of the tine.

The difference between the desired and created inter-plant distances can be referred as the inaccuracy of the system. The effect of the speed on accuracy of the thinning machine is shown in table 2

Table 2. Comparing the effect of different forward speeds on the thinning accuracy

Forward speed (km/hr)	Mean accuracy %
2	94.63
3.5	89.52
5	85.55

As it was expected, the accuracy of the machine would decrease when the speed increased. Analysis of the variances showed that there was a significant difference between the accuracies at different speeds as it is shown in figure 1.

Figure 2. Accuracy of the thinning machine in providing the desired distance between the plants at different speeds (%)

Results showed that the accuracy of the machine in retaining the optimum distance between the plants reduced when the forward speed increased. A significant difference was seen between the performance of the system between 2 km/h and 3 km/h and 5 km/h forward speed in retaining the desired distance of 20 cm between the plants however they were still in the reasonable range of 30 - 150 cm for sugar beet thinning.

In the algorithm, 60 cm spaces were considered as unthinned spaces to leave at least one sugar beet plant unthinned. This space was also changing with different forward speeds as the time needed to open and close the tine is constant, thus at higher speeds, the unthinned spaces would increase. Results showed that the minimum unthinned spaces correspond to the least speed.

Figure 3. The effect of forward speed on the distances provided between the plants

The average distance between the plants before the thinning compared to after the thinning can be seen in table 3. In this experiment 20 plants with different distances (70 to 160 mm) lying in a row were considered. The desired distance on the program was set to 200 mm. The result of the experiments showed no harm to the unthinned plants which was quite a reasonable performance.

Table 3. Average plant spaces

Average plant spaces (mm)	Status
120	Before thinning
265	After thinning
200	Set desired

The performance of the machine in retaining single plants was analysed whose result is given in table 4. The results showed that even when the speed of the machine increases from 2 to 5 km/hr, the accuracy of the machine does not decrease. It can be due to the fact that single plants are isolated from the other plants which make their detection easier whereas the mechanism has more time available to actuate the jack comparing to successive plants.

Table 4. Accuracy in retaining single plants at different forward speeds

Forward speed (km/hr)	Average accuracy in retaining single plants (%)
2	99.16 ^a
3.5	99.38 ^a
5	99.38 ^a

Similar letters in each column indicate that there is no significant difference between the groups (at 5% significance)

Conclusion

Thinning mechanism developed in this study had significantly different performances at different speeds. Among the three speeds studied in this research, the accuracy of the machine in providing the desired thinning distance between the remaining crops was gained at the speed of 2 and 3.5 km/hr where obviously the speed of 3.5 km/hr is preferred because of higher field capacity of the machine.

The machine also achieved well in leaving the single plants untouched with an accuracy of 99.1% while the speed did not have a significant influence on this achievement.

Both laboratory and field experiments showed a reasonable performance which encourages the use of automatic thinning for sugar beet cultivation.

References

- Ahmadi Moghadam P, Sheykhi Arasteh A, Komarizadeh MH, Babazadeh S 2016. Developing a selective thinning algorithm in sugar beet fields using machine vision system. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 122: 133–138.
- Jafari A, Mohtasebi SS, Eghbali H, Omid M 2006. Weed detection in sugar beet fields using machine vision. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology* 8(5): 602–605.
- Kiani S, Jafari A 2012. Crop detection and positioning in the field using discriminant analysis and neural networks based on shape features. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology* 14: 755–765.
- Palmer J, Owen GM 1971. Automatic control of sugar beet singling and thinning by means of an on-line digital computer. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering Research* 16(2): 107–125.
- Woebbecke DM, Meyer GE, Von Bargen K, Mortensen DA 1995a. Colour indices for weed identification under various soil, residue, and lighting conditions. *Transaction of the ASAE* 38(1): 259–269.